

Strength In Numbers: How Do Stellar Companions Affect Giant Planet Formation?

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The origin of the most massive extra-solar giant planets and brown dwarfs, objects with intermediate properties between stars and planets, remains unclear, with several possible formation pathways considered. In particular, the population of brown dwarfs and giant planets orbiting around their host stars from very close orbital separations is still challenging to reconcile with theories of formation and evolution. Stellar binaries have long been neglected in exoplanet science, with many selection effects and biases against binaries present in observational surveys, and theoretical models of planet formation primarily focused on single stars. However, with over half of the stars in our Galaxy being part of binary or higher-order multiple systems [1], studying binaries as environments for exoplanets is essential to achieve a complete overview of the diversity and origins of exoplanetary systems.

The dominant finding emerging from studies of exoplanets in binary star systems is the idea that tight binary companions, with separations of tens of au, prevent the formation or survival of planets, observationally confirmed through a strong deficit of exoplanets in such binaries [2]. Nonetheless, slightly wider binaries, on separation scales of hundreds of au, may be less detrimental to the existence of planets, and could even help planet migration processes via secular interactions with the planets [3]. In addition, early surveys suggested that massive giant planets and brown dwarf companions on tight orbits may be predominantly found in wide binary systems, and that these inner planetary companions in multiple-star systems may show distinct physical and orbital properties to the rest of the exoplanet population [4].

Recently, we confirmed the robustness of these findings [5], measuring that $\sim 80\%$ of stars hosting a planet or brown dwarf above $7 M_{\text{Jup}}$ and within 1 au have an outer binary companion on the separation range 20–10,000 au. This indicates that stellar multiplicity likely plays a role in the existence and properties of these massive planetary and brown dwarf companions, although the precise nature and extend of this role is still not understood.

Compilation of planets in binaries

In order to place these results into a wider context, we gathered the largest compilation to date of planets in wide binary star systems, presented in [6]. From a sample of 938 stars hosting 1326 confirmed exoplanets and brown dwarfs within 200 pc, we identified from existing literature information and the Gaia catalogues 218 hosts to have visual stellar companions, confirmed to be co-moving with the primary star. The companion separations extend from <1 au for the most extreme case to 20,000 au, the outer limit placed on the companion search, with companion masses ranging from the hydro-

gen burning-limit to several Solar masses, resulting in a wide diversity of systems.

The obtained compilation provides a raw binary fraction of $23.2 \pm 1.6\%$ for planetary hosts, with a $2.2\text{-}\sigma$ difference between single-planet systems ($25.1 \pm 1.9\%$) and multi-planet systems ($18.0 \pm 2.7\%$). An even larger $3.6\text{-}\sigma$ difference was observed in multiplicity rate between stars harbouring giant planets or brown dwarfs, with masses above $0.1 M_{\text{Jup}}$ ($25.5 \pm 1.8\%$), and those hosting sub-Jovian planets ($16.6 \pm 1.7\%$), a trend that seems to be further emphasised as we look at higher-mass and shorter-separation planets and brown dwarfs.

Figure 1: Semi-major axes against masses of all planets and brown dwarfs in the studied compilation, showing those around single stars in blue and those in binary star systems in magenta.

While underlying biases from the original planet discovery surveys and incompleteness effects in the binary search were not accounted or corrected for in this study, the gathered compilation may also be used to investigate if or how stellar multiplicity impacts planet properties across various regions of the planetary parameter space (Figure 1). Detailed analyses comparing the distributions of planetary semi-major axes and masses between those orbiting apparently single stars and those found in binary systems confirmed the excess of close-in, massive giant planets and brown dwarfs in binaries, compared to less massive planets, and to wider, warm and cool giants.

Effect of binary separation

To understand how the observed stellar companions may be affecting the formation or architectures of the inner planets and brown dwarfs, we investigated the binary separations of all the systems in our sample with an exo-

planet or brown dwarf within 0.5 au and above $0.1 M_{\text{Jup}}$. This analysis revealed that short-period giant planets identified in very wide binaries, with binary separations beyond 1000 au, show the same mass and semi-major axis distributions as close-in giant exoplanets orbiting single stars (Figure 2). This suggests that such distant stellar companions do not influence the final properties and orbital configurations of the inner planets.

Figure 2: Planet semi-major axes (left) and masses (right) as a function of binary separation for all planets with masses above $0.1 M_{\text{Jup}}$ and semi-major axes within 0.5 au. The dashed black lines show the distributions for planets in the same mass and semi-major axis ranges found to be orbiting single stars.

On the other hand, we found that the excess of massive and close-in planets in binaries mostly appear to be in binary systems with separations of several hundreds au, and that planets and brown dwarfs in such binaries tend to show larger masses and/or shorter orbital separations than the planetary population around single stars or very wide binaries (Figure 2). These findings therefore indicate that outer stellar companions located at several hundred au are able to influence the formation or evolution of the observed giant planets and brown dwarfs, with the mechanisms at play seemingly resulting in the formed inner companions reaching higher masses and tighter orbital configurations than those forming around single stars.

Disk fragmentation triggered by binary companions

The trends found between stellar multiplicity and different exoplanet populations are observed for the most massive planets and brown dwarfs only. We thus investigated the possible effects of outer binary companions on giant planet formation through gravitational instability (GI) in circumstellar disks, since this process primarily produces massive planetary and substellar companions, in contrast to the core accretion mechanism. We therefore adapted simulations of self-gravitating disks [7] to binary environments, adding outer stellar companions around $0.2 M_{\odot}$ disks that were found to be stable and unable to fragment in standard single-star environments.

Testing various binary semi-major axes, we found that the added external stellar companions were successfully able to induce fragmentation in otherwise-stable disks, when on intermediate separations of \sim few hundred au, as shown in Figure 3 [8]. However, closer-in companions within \sim 100 au were found to be too disruptive, while wider binaries beyond several hundred au had no effect on the disk evolution, which remained stable as in the single-star case. Exploring a range of binary configurations (varying the binary eccentricity, inclination, companion mass), we found that this optimal range is a function of the various binary elements, resulting in a sweet spot of binary configurations over which outer companions are able to trigger GI fragmentation, and lead to the formation of giant planets or brown dwarfs. GI induced by intermediate-separation stellar companions may hence be able to explain the origin of the observed excess of massive giant planets and brown dwarfs in such binaries.

References

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Figure 3: Simulations of self-gravitating disks with outer stellar companions on binary separations ranging from 100 au to 400 au. The added binary companions with separations of 150–250 au were able to successfully trigger the fragmentation of the disk.

Short CV

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